

Reassessing hospitality competencies in the post-pandemic era: The Philippines' hospitality management program as an example

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Abstract

Almost without exception, when it comes to academic hospitality research, one of the most frequently investigated topics is competencies. Many academics have spent the last three decades trying to define what it means to be successful in the hospitality industry, and they have come up with a variety of different definitions. Despite the large number of studies that have been conducted, there appears to be a consistent lack of consistency in terms of methodology and findings. A second issue is that the vast majority of these studies have a limited geographic scope, which may understate the unique and complex hospitality environments that can be found in Southeast Asia, Europe, United States of America, and Africa, among other locations. As a departure from previous research, this study focuses on the perceptions of hospitality professionals in the Philippines, a popular Southeast Asian tourist destination, as to the most important competencies required for a successful career there. This study is still looking into how hospitality graduates who enter the industry after the pandemic develop these skills. The Philippines is one of the most popular tourist destinations in Southeast Asia. Those involved in the private and public sectors, as well as those in academia, will find the findings to be useful.

Keywords: Industry; hospitality; competencies; education.

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Introduction

Because it is a global "people" enterprise, higher education in the hospitality and tourism industry contributes to the development of the industry's future leaders. Both student participation and subsequent student satisfaction have been shown to be distinguishing characteristics of high-quality course delivery in the past. In order to explain these findings, the three pillars of the Community of Inquiry framework must first be understood: cognitive presence, teaching presence, and social (peer) presence. COVID-19 is still a serious public health concern, and the findings of this study are relevant to that concern (Orlowski et al., 2021). In the opinion of many, education's primary goal should be to produce workers who are capable of meeting the demands and challenges of their chosen profession (Christou, 2002; Hansson, 2001 as cited in Cetinkaya et al., 2012). Academics have attempted to identify the "success" abilities required for careers in the hospitality industry using a variety of techniques and over the course of the last 30 years (Tas et al., 1996). Because "...there appears to be inconsistency in the methodology applied, the competencies under examination, and real competences revealed as most or least relevant," according to Zopiatis (2010), such findings should be treated with caution.

Taking a novel approach to the "success" competencies of the hospitality industry, this study seeks to add to the existing body of knowledge by introducing new concepts and theories (Anthony, 2015). Primary objective of the study is to interview hospitality professionals in order to determine which competencies they believe are most important for a successful career in the industry, as well as how much these competencies are developed by hospitality graduates as they begin their careers in the field.

Literature Review

Academics from a wide range of disciplines have investigated the abilities required in the hospitality industry. Academia has produced an avalanche of competency definitions over the course of several decades. The definition of competency proposed by Boyatzis (1991) is in contrast, the definition proposed by Spencer and Spencer (1993) is "*any personal trait that has been shown to be associated with a person's ability to perform to a high standard under pressure in a given situation or job.*" Accuracy can be defined as: "*A set of skills and qualities that are necessary to perform a specific task effectively and efficiently in accordance with specified quantifiable organizational criteria capable of meeting specific goals.*" Zopiatis et al. (2015) defines competency as "*the personal traits and talents required to accomplish a pre-described task effectively and efficiently in accordance with specified quantifiable organizational criteria capable of meeting specific goals.*"

To try to understand this complicated subject from a variety of perspectives, scholars have developed and applied competency frameworks to their research efforts (Katz, 2009). Among other categories, Richard Feynman, one of the field's pioneers, proposed a paradigm in which skills could be divided into three distinct domains: technical skills, human skills, and conceptual skills, among other categories. Katz (2009) developed a model that served as the foundation for Sandwith (1993) to develop his which is unquestionably the most frequently cited framework in the hospitality literature. which was developed as a second paradigm that has been widely used in similar investigations since its development (Dimmock et al., 2003). The Competing Values Framework, which is based on four traditional organizational theory models, proposes eight managerial leadership roles, including mentor, facilitator, monitor, coordinator, and director. These roles are based on four traditional organizational theory models. In addition, the roles are divided into four categories: producer, broker, and innovator, among others. Positions available include other examples include mentor, facilitator and monitor; coordinator and director; producer and broker.

Over the years, tourism and hospitality researchers have conducted a large number of studies on skills (Kwok et al., 2012). Nonetheless, caution must be exercised when attempting to make sense of the data and safely draw some inferences from it, despite the sheer volume of information available. When viewed through the eyes of even the most knowledgeable hospitality reader, factors such as the technique used, the sample size, the geographic location, the conceptual framework used (if any), and the distinctiveness of the specific hospitality sector can send conflicting messages about the industry.

Methodology

Aiming to better understand hospitality professionals' perceptions of the most crucial skills required for a successful career, as well as the extent to which graduates of the hospitality industry acquire these skills, the researchers conducted this study. This research will aid in the further investigation of "success" competencies in the hospitality industry, as well as the addition of new knowledge to the already existing body of knowledge (Marneros et al., 2020). Three research questions were developed in order to reflect the study's primary goal more accurately, and they are listed below:

RQ1. Which competencies do hospitality professionals believe are critical for achieving a successful career in hospitality?

RQ2: To what extent do hospitality graduates who enter the industry acquire these skills and abilities? In terms of age, gender, educational background, managerial level, and functional/operational area are all important factors to consider how professionals' perceptions differ?

RQ3. Do professionals' perceptions differ in terms of age, gender, educational background, managerial level, and functional / operational area which are all important factors to consider?

In order to answer the three research questions that have been proposed, a quantitative survey will be carried out.

The survey will include thirty competency statements that are divided into five competency domains that are closely related to Sandwith's (2018) model of competency development. Each of the thirty statements will be evaluated on its perceived importance, and respondents will be asked to comment on the extent to which these competencies are developed by hospitality graduates who enter the industry.

When analyzing the data and trying to find answers to the research questions, we will use both descriptive and inferential statistics. These will include frequency distributions, reliability analysis (Cronbach's Alpha), independent sample t-tests, and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Also included will be a quadrant analysis to create a two-by-two matrix of the competencies under investigation based on whether they are perceived to be of high or low importance, as well as whether they are perceived to be of high or low development when graduates first enter the industry, among other things.

With the help of a quantitative survey, the researchers collected information from individuals (n=186) who are currently employed in full-time managerial positions in hotel establishments throughout the Philippines. Route of administration, the structured questionnaire were pilot-tested for reliability and validity with a panel of experts drawn from both academia and industry, using the test-retest method, before being administered to the general public. Minor revisions to the original survey were made in response to the experts' comments and suggestions, in order to make it more user-friendly overall. It was decided whether to administer the surveys through the mail or through direct personalized distribution to the general managers of the hotels and two department heads of the departments in which they worked.

Data were analyzed using Cronbach's Alpha, the independent sample t test, and one-way ANOVA, to answer the research questions. When graduates first entered the workforce, they were divided into four quadrants according to how important they were to employers and how far along they were in their development in those competencies. The results of this quadrant analysis were used to create a two-by-two matrix of the investigated competencies. Quadrant analysis, on the other hand, has been used in a variety of hospitality studies (Cobanoglu et al., 2011) and is especially useful because it is a "low-cost, easily understood technique that can yield significant insights" (Martilla & James, 1977).

Results and Discussion

It was distributed to a total of 186 hotel managers in full-time management positions in the Philippines who completed the questionnaires. Demographic information about those who took the survey is shown in the following table, which includes details such as age group, gender, and educational background, as well as job function.

Table 1. The profile of the respondents (n=186)

Category	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Female	43	23.12%
	Male	143	76.88%
Age	Over 50 years old	27	14.52%
	41 – 50 years old	93	50.00%
	31 – 40 years old	42	22.58%
	18 – 30 years old	24	12.90%
Educational Background	High school	73	39.25%
	Undergraduate	71	38.17%
	Graduate degree	42	22.58%
Managerial Level	Rank and file	30	16.13%
	Middle level (superior)	87	46.77%
	Upper level (heads)	69	37.10%
Functional Areas	Management / top administration	70	37.63%
	Food and beverage / culinary	72	38.71%
	Rooms division / front office	29	15.59%
	Other	15	8.06%

In the wake of the pandemic, the researchers set out to discover which skills and abilities are needed for the selected Filipino hospitality professionals. There are several prerequisites for a successful career in the country's burgeoning tourism industry. In Table 2, there were 30 statements in this study. It was discovered that human relations and communication skills were the most important, followed by operational knowledge, leadership, human resources management, and financial analysis.

Maintaining a professional appearance and poise, as well as complying with sanitary and safety standards, ranked high on the list of individual competencies. Managing guest issues with understanding and sensitivity was ranked third in the list of competencies. The survey participants ranked financial analysis competencies at the bottom of the list when it came to importance in the workplace.

Those polled placed human relations and communication at the top of their list of priorities for professional development, followed by operational expertise and leadership, as well as a thorough understanding of human resource management. Topping the list was effective interaction with coworkers and customers, followed closely by effective collaboration with coworkers and observance of sanitary and safety standards of care. Keeping a polished demeanor and poise were also highly regarded. Despite their similar ranking, there are differences in the perceived importance and actual development of all five competency categories. Because of this, a quadrant analysis was performed to better understand the relationship between perceived actual development and attributed importance.

Table 2. Competency analysis

Competency Categories	Importance			Actual Development				
	Mean (Reliability Alpha Cronbach)	Std. Dev.	Rank in Category (Overall Rank)	Overall Category Rank	Mean (Reliability Alpha Cronbach)	Std. Dev.	Rank in Category (Overall Rank)	Overall Category Rank
COMP 1: Leadership (7 items)	4.15 (.783)	.469		3	3.76 (.916)	.779		3
Taking charge of and supervising the work of other people	4.19	.739	3 (14)		3.63	.974	6 (25)	
Changing one's behavior in response to changing circumstances	4.08	.657	5 (20)		3.47	.998	7 (30)	
Creating new and creative ways of working	3.87	.685	7 (26)		3.65	.971	5 (23)	
Making decisions under time constraints or in a crisis situation is difficult.	4.15	.802	4 (17)		3.81	1.032	3 (16)	
Keeping up to date with industry practices and new developments is essential.	4.05	.684	6 (22)		3.79	.885	4 (17)	
The ability to maintain a professional appearance and poise	4.45	.666	1 (3)		4.05	.890	1 (5)	
Being ethical in one's behavior.	4.24	.736	2 (11)		3.94	.934	2 (9)	
COMP 2: Financial Analysis (4 items)	3.74 (.881)	.797		5	3.60 (.905)	.874		5
Techniques of financial analysis are employed.	3.68	.859	3 (29)		3.50	.914	4 (29)	
The factors that influence the controllability of profits are being investigated.	3.76	.839	2 (28)		3.71	.960	1 (19)	
Using historical and current data to forecast future revenue and expense for the department	3.84	.956	1 (27)		3.61	1.024	2 (26)	
Examining financial and statistical reports on a weekly, monthly, and annual basis	3.68	1.047	4 (30)		3.58	1.059	3 (27)	
COMP 3: Human Resources Management (5 items)	4.07 (.784)	.642		4	3.65 (.873)	.762		4
Employees must be motivated in order to achieve desired results.	4.27	.768	2 (9)		3.69	.946	2 (21)	
Personnel are being chosen and assigned.	3.97	.844	3 (23)		3.68	.966	3 (22)	
Employee performance is being evaluated.	3.89	.884	5 (25)		3.53	.982	5 (28)	
Setting quality standards for employees and defining those standards	4.29	.833	1 (7)		3.69	.856	1 (20)	
Providing employees with access to information is important.	3.92	.850	4 (24)		3.63	.922	4 (24)	
COMP 4: Human Relations – Communication (7 items)	4.31 (.826)	.470		1	4.01 (.940)	.764		1
Effectively communicating with coworkers and supervisors	4.40	.582	3 (5)		4.06	.916	3 (4)	
Communication with clients and customers in an effective manner	4.50	.668	1 (1)		4.16	.904	1 (1)	
Has the ability to communicate effectively in both written and oral form.	4.21	.746	5 (13)		3.89	.866	6 (12)	
Interacts with a diverse range of people without difficulty.	4.16	.654	6 (16)		3.82	.836	7 (15)	
Increasing respect and appreciation for differences and individual differences among people.	4.06	.671	7 (21)		3.92	.791	5 (11)	
Managing problems with guests in a sensitive and understanding manner	4.48	.737	2 (2)		4.05	.890	4 (6)	
Participating as a member of a group	4.37	.630	4 (6)		4.16	.886	2 (2)	
COMP 5: Operational Knowledge (7 items)	4.23 (.850)	.526		2	3.93 (.927)	.738		2
Using front-desk (computer) equipment to its full potential	4.08	.924	7 (19)		3.85	.898	6 (14)	
Providing service by anticipating the wants and needs of the guest	4.29	.683	2 (8)		3.97	.952	3 (8)	
working knowledge of the product-service relationship	4.27	.701	3 (10)		3.92	.924	4 (10)	
Identifying and categorizing operational difficulties	4.11	.723	6 (18)		3.71	.889	7 (18)	
Follows hygiene and safety regulations to ensure that the organization complies.	4.42	.776	1 (4)		4.15	.933	1 (3)	

Note:

IMPORTANCE: There are five levels on this scale: 1 means no importance, 2 means no importance; 3 indicates neutrality; 4 indicates importance, and 5 indicates essentiality.

ACTUAL DEVELOPMENT: 1 = Very Poor, 2 = Below Average, 3 = Average, 4 = Above Average, and 5 = Excellent;

Quadrant Analysis

For this purpose, quadrant analysis was used to better understand how graduates' perceived importance of competencies compared to their actual development in the hospitality industry. The findings were put to good use in delineating the interrelationships. As a diagrammatic technique, quadrant analysis uses a rectangular grid to represent mean importance and development results on a two-dimensional grid. There are four quadrants in the grid that are based on the importance (low vs. high) and level of development of each competency (low vs. high).

The cross-hairs used to divide the matrix into four quadrants, as shown in Table 4, have an effect on how we interpret the results of this experiment. Following Martilla and James (1977), mean values of 4.14 (median = 4.18) and 3.81 (median = 3.88) for importance cross hair line and development, respectively, were used. Martilla and James (1977) recommended these values.

Table 3. Importance-development quadrant analysis

HIGH IMPORTANCE	<p>QIII (High I – Low D)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human resource management (HRM) is the process of identifying and implementing quality standards that all employees must adhere to • Managing the work of others (HRM) • Deciding on, directing, and monitoring their progress (LED) 	<p>QIV (High I – High D)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effectively communicating with coworkers and supervisors (HRC) • Ability to communicate effectively with clients and customers (HRC) • Participating as a member of a group (HRC) • Assuring that the organization is adhering to hygiene and safety standards (OK) • Maintaining a professional demeanor and poise at all times (LED) • Dealing sensitively and understandingly with problems that arise among guests (HRC) • Becoming fluent in the industry's basic lingo (OK) • Being able to anticipate customers' wants and needs in order to provide excellent service (LED) • Ability to communicate both orally and in writing effectively in a product-service environment (HRC) • Understanding the realities of this type of work (OK) • The ability to work with a diverse group of people is second nature to him (HRC) • The ability to make quick decisions in a time of need, or during a crisis (LED)
	<p>QI (Low I – Low D)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Following current industry practices and new developments is essential (LED) • Identifying and defining operational issues that may arise (OK) • Choosing and reassigning members of staff (HRM) • Creating new and creative ways of working (LED) • Enabling employees to have access to relevant information (HRM) • Predicting future departmental revenues and expenses based on historical and current data (FIN) • Examining financial and statistical reports (FIN) on a weekly, monthly, and annual basis. • Examining factors affecting the profits' controllability (FIN) • Human resource management (HRM) • Financial analysis procedures (FIN) • Flexibility in response to changing circumstances (LED) 	<p>QII (Low I – High D)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fostering a sense of tolerance and acceptance of one's own uniqueness and the differences among people (HRC) • Making the most of front-office (computer) technology (OK)
LOW	<p>LOW HIGH</p> <p>The development level of graduates who enter the industry</p>	

Note that in table 3, Human Resource Management (HRM), Human Relations and Communication (HRC), and Operational Knowledge (OK) all fall under the umbrella term "Leadership Competencies" (LED).

According to the survey respondents, the skills and knowledge found in Quadrant I are both of low priority and development level. Four financial analysis competencies, three leadership competencies, three HR competencies, and only one operational knowledge competency were found. Quadrant two of this quadrant contains all seven of the leadership competencies as well as three of the human resources management competencies. A high level of development is seen in Quadrant II competencies, but their significance is considered to be relatively low. To be included in this category, one must "*promote appreciation of diversity and individual differences*" and "*use front-office equipment effectively.*" Employee quality standards, employee motivation, and employee direction and supervision are all responsibilities of stakeholders, all of which fall under the purview of Quadrant III.

Despite their importance, the development of these three skills is lacking. Finally, there are fourteen skills in Quadrant IV that have been identified as particularly important and in need of development. Six of the seven competencies in human relations and communication, as well as five of the seven competencies in operational knowledge, are included here.

If there were any statistically significant differences between new professionals' perceptions of how much they value their skills compared to their actual progress in acquiring those skills, this study was conducted. This problem was addressed using a variety of t-tests and ANOVAs, in addition to post hoc multiple comparison tests, by the researchers (Tukey Honest Significant Difference).

As a result of this study, there were significant differences in the competencies of HR management, human relations/communication, financial analysis, and leadership ($f=7.324$; $p=.00000$) according to age ($f=3.941$; $p=.009$, 4.042 ; $p=.008$). When it comes to giving a higher value to a certain factor, those who are younger than 30 are more likely than those who are older. When it comes to the actual level of development, there are differences among the five competency categories. As with the importance ratings, responses from those between the ages of 20 and 30 place a greater emphasis on actual development across all five categories. Males place a higher value on human resource management competencies than females ($t=3.321$; $p=.001$), according to one statistically significant difference. There were no significant differences in the level of development of graduates entering the industry between the respondents.

There were statistically significant differences ($p<0.05$) in all five competency categories when it came to importance. Higher-educated survey takers placed a higher value on each of the five categories than did those with less education. With this in mind, statistically significant differences were found when comparing actual development to expectations in three of the five competency categories. It was found that only operational knowledge and leadership skills differed. Human relations / communication ($f=4.950$; $p=.008$) and financial analysis ($f=3.165$; $p=.008$) showed significant differences in importance at the managerial level.

Human relations and communication are more important to those in upper and middle management positions, while financial analysis and financial planning are more important to those in entry-level management positions. Human relations / communication ($f=4.576$; $p=.0012$) as well as the actual development of operational knowledge differed ($f=5.762$; $p=.004$) from expectations. Respondents in mid-level management and their counterparts at the upper and lower levels report significant differences in development.

Respondents' perceptions of the relative importance of the five categories vary by functional or operational area by three standard deviations. Furthermore, there are differences in human relations/communication, operational knowledge ($f=3.451$; $p=.001$) and technical knowledge ($f=3.451$; $p\text{-value} = 0.001$).

There was also financial analysis ($f=6.047$; $p=.001$; $p=.018$) carried out on this data set. Respondents in the food and beverage division rated financial analysis skills significantly lower than those in upper management, rooms, and other divisions. For the five retained competencies, the findings showed that there was no statistically significant difference in actual development.

Conclusion

The study's specific goal was to find out how important industry professionals in the Philippines think hospitality skills are (De Guzman et al., 2020). Additionally, the research adds to our understanding of the value placed on interpersonal and communication skills as well as operational knowledge in the hospitality industry by professionals. According to Zopiatis (2010), the study's findings do not support the notion advanced by a number of academics industry-specific knowledge is being displaced by generic management competencies, particularly finance. Findings from the survey revealed that participants had a very low opinion of their own ability to conduct financial analysis.

It is important to pay special attention to the three competencies that industry professionals believe are critical to success, even though many hospitality graduates entering the workforce lack these skills. According to the authors, formal management development programs and other initiatives should consider the three competencies, which are particularly relevant to human resources and leadership. The difficulty of developing skills like the ability to motivate, direct, and supervise others in a purely theoretical and academic environment must also be considered. The ability of newly hired employees to handle such operational demands will almost certainly be enhanced by a trial run in a real-world hospitality environment.

According to the findings of the study, statistically significant differences were discovered in the demographics and other characteristics of the respondents. While all skill sets are valued more highly by younger hospitality professionals (those aged 20 to 30), only operational knowledge is valued more highly by this generation, which is interesting because they represent the newest generation of hospitality professionals. On the other hand, people with higher academic credentials place greater emphasis on each of the five competencies. In both cases, general management knowledge appears to be more important than it was previously, which suggests that attitudes toward its acquisition have shifted toward more western ideals in recent years.

Generalizing these findings should be done with caution because they are based on the viewpoints of a homogeneous sample (all full-time hospitality managers) rather than a representative sample of the industry as a whole. Teachers who are currently developing or delivering related courses can use the findings to help students better understand the current needs of the industry, and hospitality professionals can use them to help new hires in their respective industries learn specific skills that are in demand in their respective industries. In addition, educators should involve representatives from the industry in the development and revision of academic curricula. The reluctance of academics to involve hospitality professionals in such a critical function could result in programs that are unable to meet even the most basic requirements of the industry itself, which would be disastrous.

Lastly, the new information generated as a result of this research may spur academics to conduct additional research on this subject in their respective fields from a variety of perspectives in order to advance their own careers in that field. According to the authors, academics should investigate how competencies relate to both individual success (such as developing one's career) and organizational success (such as achieving organizational goals) (for example, competencies in relation to cultural and management style differences). In an era of unprecedented change and uncertainty, all stakeholders must keep a close eye on the "success" competencies of the hospitality professions in order to define, cultivate, and promote these skills and competencies.

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